

*Biomuse Trio*

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Biomuse Trio is a composition for biomuse, violin and laptop. The strengths of each instrument are fused into a chamber music composition that emphasizes precise, coordinated musical interaction. There is a particular interest to explore the human body as musical instrument, and thus the various prosthetics of the Biomuse are hidden in performance.